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Title:

Philosophical Analysis of Free Will and Determinism in the Seminary Context: Insight from BF Skinner, Viktor Frankl, and Jordan Peterson

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Abstract:

Determinism and free will have been debated since the ancient era, and even during the contemporary period, this is still a hot concern. In particular, the seminary formation, whether seminarians are caused by the seminary rule of life or caused by their own free will. With that, the researcher sought the aid of BF Skinner, Viktor Frankl, and Jordan Peterson. BF Skinner views determinism as a behavior modifier through a design like the Seminary Rule of Life. Viktor Frankl's insights suggest that a seminarian's behavior is determined by their own free will through their purpose to become a priest. Then, through Jordan Peterson, the rift mends through his idea of balance between chaos and order, saying that the primary source of behavior is purpose. Still, it needs guidance from a design since man's free will alone is immature. Using the three insights, seminarians' free will and determining seminary rule of life will reconcile.

Keywords: *Determinism, Free Will, Seminary Formation, Seminary Rule of Life, Purposes*

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**Philosophical Analysis of Free Will and Determinism in the Seminary Context:
Insight from BF Skinner, Viktor Frankl, and Jordan Peterson**

**Presented to the Instructor of Philosophical Synthesis 2
in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements of the Course Bachelor of Arts in Philosophy of
San Isidro College**

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Abstract
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Determinism and free will have been debated since the ancient era, and even during the contemporary period, this is still a hot concern. In particular, the seminary formation, whether seminarians are caused by the seminary rule of life or caused by their own free will. With that, the researcher sought the aid of BF Skinner, Viktor Frankl, and Jordan Peterson. BF Skinner views determinism as a behavior modifier through a design like the Seminary Rule of Life. Viktor Frankl's insights suggest that a seminarian's behavior is determined by their own free will through their purpose to become a priest. Then, through Jordan Peterson, the rift mends through his idea of balance between chaos and order, saying that the primary source of behavior is purpose. Still, it needs guidance from a design since man's free will alone is immature. Using the three insights, seminarians' free will and determining seminary rule of life will reconcile.

Key Words: Determinism, Free Will, Seminary Formation, Seminary Rule of Life, Purposes

Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM

Background of the Study

Determinism is the philosophical view that entails human actions or behaviors are out of man's control since external factors have control of them (e.g., God, Cosmos, Atoms, Religion, Constitution, etc.). On the contrary, free will means that a person has control of his/her actions, and external factors have no power to control someone. With that, is there a chance that determinism and free will would work together considering the fact that they are diametrically opposed? How do philosophers argue this problem? This problem had already arrived a long time ago. For example, in medieval times, they had the idea that God anticipates the future, and we have nothing to do with it. "Suppose that God does this not by directly coercing us to do things that we don't want to do but, rather, by implanting the desire in us to do what God wants us to do."¹

However, as the contemporary era arrived, the idea of determinism changed. From theistic determinism, it turns to existentialism, because that era is the rise of existentialist philosophers as well as the psychologies. An example of this was Nietzsche, who criticized the will controlling religion, and Sigmund Freud, who was the father of psychology. Moreover, the contemporary era is more advanced in knowledge, where they criticize the limits of traditional forms of determinism and acknowledge that human actions are processes of mind in the nervous system. With that, the researcher focuses on the contemporary idea of determinism, particularly the philosophy of BF Skinner. He is an atheist psychologist whose idea of determinism focuses only on "actions that are

¹ Matthew Van Cleave, "The Problem of Free Will and Determinism," University of Central Florida, March 17, 2023, <https://pressbooks.online.ucf.edu/introductiontophilosophy/chapter/the-problem-of-free-will-and-determinism/>.

governed by external forces.”² Then, these external forces (such as religion or laws) will create man’s behavior.

Victor Frankl, on the other hand, is a proponent of free will. In his book entitled “Man Search for Meaning,” it says that man is free to choose and free not to choose “because they had a purpose, their lives had a meaning.”³ Then, the researcher adds the philosophy of Jordan Peterson to harmonize determinism and free will. It provides an understanding of why external forces are necessary. Using his book, the “12 Rules for Life,” and his videos, this paper shows how Peterson “provides a firm set of guidelines to help achieve balance in our lives because life is full of unknowns and can be chaotic.”⁴

The context of this study is the St. John XXIII Seminary, where all the variables can be found applicable. Essentially, the seminary determines the seminarians' behavior through a design named the St. John XXIII College Seminary Rule of Life. Though it is stipulated on the back page of St. John XXIII College Seminary Rule of Life that the “guidelines are by no means understood as restrictions of basic freedom of seminarians,”⁵ bear in mind that freedom is not interchangeable with the word free will. Thus, this creates a question: if seminarians have free will if they are under a seminary rule of life, who determines behavior?

Plus, Section 4 of the Rule of Life entails that seminarians are bound to disciplinary action if they do not follow the guidelines well. Paragraph B of Section 4 says that “the formators

² IvyPanda. 2021. "Response to Arguments Made by B.F. Skinner." Last modified September 10, 2021. <https://ivypanda.com/essays/response-to-arguments-made-by-bf-skinner/>.

³ Emir Zecovic, “Man Search for Meaning Summary,” 12 min, March 11, 2024, <https://blog.12min.com/mans-search-for-meaning-pdf-summary/>.

⁴ Jordan Peterson, “12 Rules for Life Summary,” Briefer, accessed on April 23, 2024, <https://briefer.com/books/12-rules-life>.

⁵ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors’ Board, *Seminary Rule of Life* (St. John XXIII College Seminary, Paling, Patpat, City of Malaybalay, 2022), back page.

determine if the seminarian under disciplinary action should be sent home or render due recompense inside the seminary.”⁶ Thus, seminarians’ free will is questionable due to the reinforcing punishment of the design that determines behavior. However, the researcher intends to use a compatible claim. Answering that despite following the rule of life, seminarians are still to practice their free will.

In particular, this proposed thesis aims to give knowledge to seminarians that seminary formation does not control seminarians' actions. Unfolding its relevance would be a great help for the seminarians to purify their vocation. Then, the perspective of the three philosophers would then help make the claims and arguments concrete towards the seminary formation. In line with this, the researcher believes that this study would help seminarians improve not just their motivation but also their discipline of self toward answering God’s call.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to explore the interplay of determinism of the rule of life and free will of the seminarians towards vocation to priesthood using the ideas of BF Skinner, Victor Frankl, and Jordan Peterson.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the views of BF Skinner, Viktor Frankl, and Jordan Peterson on free will and determinism?
2. How does Jordan Peterson’s idea put together the concepts of determinism of BF Skinner and Viktor Frankl’s free will?

⁶ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors’ Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 26.

3. How can the views of BF Skinner, Viktor Frankl, and Jordan Peterson illustrate the co-existence of the determining rule of life and seminarians' free will?

Objectives of the Study

The goal of the study is to:

- a. Explore the different ideas of BF Skinner, Viktor Frankl, and Jordan Peterson on free will and determinism.
- b. Explores how Jordan Peterson's idea integrates the concepts of determinism of BF Skinner and Viktor Frankl's free will.
- c. Create a comprehensive explanation of BF Skinner, Viktor Frankl, and Jordan Peterson in illustrating the co-existence of the determining rule of life and seminarians' free will.

Argument Design

This study is supported by three theories. The theory of determinism is anchored on BF Skinner's operant conditioning. This theory states that our actions are governed by external forces. Then, these external forces (such as religion or laws) create man's behavior. To emphasize more, operant conditioning involves positive and negative reinforcement and punishment. Positive reinforcement rewards people for wanting to do the desired action. Then, negative reinforcement is the removal of unpleasant things from the person to increase good behavior, and the consequence is punishing people to refrain from unwanted actions.

The theory of free will is anchored on Victor Frankl's logotherapy. It is a therapeutic approach that helps the person to pursue meaning and to choose despite any given set of

circumstances freely. Moreover, the theory also entails that humans can transcend external circumstances through conscious choice.

Lastly, the study also anchors on Jordan Peterson's pragmatism and existential psychology as a synthesis of two opposites. Using Jordan Peterson's insight about the balance of chaos and order, the researcher provides the necessity of determinism without denying man's free will.

The framework indicates that there is interplay between determinism and free will. In particular, the theories are in line with seminary formation. For instance, the rule of life is the determiner, while seminarians do the will. Then, using Jordan Peterson's insight, the researchers synthesize the importance of both.

Fig. 1. The Synthesis of Determinism and Free Will using *Convergent Argument*.

Significance of the Study

The problem of the seminary rule of life is the thought that it determines the seminarian's behavior towards its vocation to the priesthood. However, the researcher aims to make the determining "seminary rule of life" compatible with the seminarians' free will. With that, it is also necessary to know who will benefit from this study. And so, the paper aims to contribute to the field of philosophy, to enhance formation, to help the seminarians, as well as the seminary as a whole.

First, in the field of philosophy. The study helps deepen the understanding of determinism and free will that debates started a long time ago. The study also provides more knowledge to its branch, namely existentialism, which is a philosophy that focuses on human existence, particularly its search for meaning and authenticity.

Second, to society in general but most importantly to the formation in particular. The study helps people understand how important rules and regulations are. As a result, the study helps the government administration in implementing good rules for the formation of its members, and the members will be encouraged to appreciate rules for the formation of themselves.

Third, for the seminarians. The compatibility of determinism and free will may help them understand their way of life, purify their vocation, and learn to master how to will accordingly.

Lastly, for the seminary, the study will provide some bases on how to assess well those seminarians who desire to become priests.

Scope and Delimitation

The study focused on exploring the interplay of determinism and free will and its relevance to seminary formation. In particular, the word determinism focuses only on psychological determinism, in which the behavior or mindset of someone is controlled by rules set by a particular group. Then the object of the researcher for determinism is the seminary rule of life in line with the operant conditioning of BF Skinner, one of the attributes of psychological determinism. And for free will, the subjects are limited to the seminarians of St. John XXIII seminary in line with the insights of Victor Frankl. Lastly, the idea of Jordan Peterson is used only to collide the two opposing ideas. Moreover, the study is limited to existentialism philosophy as a particular field of research.

Definition of Terms

Determinism. The theory is that human beliefs and actions follow an unavoidable anterior psychological condition.⁷ This suggests that an individual lacks true choice since their behavior and decisions are preordained by the conditions set by the planner.

Free will. The power of enacting choices or decisions made by the mind.⁸ In this study, free will is measured as an ability to choose what attitude one would respond to in difficult circumstances.

Seminarian. A man who is discerning the Lord's call to the Roman Catholic priesthood.⁹

⁷ Roy Weatherford, "Psychological Determinism," Taylor Francis, accessed on April 23, 2024, <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/mono/10.4324/9781315203003-14/psychological-determinism-roy-weatherford>.

⁸ Grant Bartley, "What is Free Will?" Philosophy Now, accessed on April 23, 2024, https://philosophynow.org/issues/159/What_Is_Free_Will#:~:text=The%20power%20of%20the%20will,by%20a%20mind%20from%20possibilities.

⁹ "What is a seminarian?" Saint John Paul II Seminary, accessed on April 23, 2024, <https://jp2seminary.org/what-is-a-seminarian-1>.

Seminary: A college for training people to become priests or ministers.¹⁰ In particular, this seminary is located at Pal-ing, Patpat, Malaybalay City, under the see of the Diocese of Malaybalay.

St. John XXIII Seminary Rule of Life. A structured framework or set of guidelines that serve as a basis for seminary formation and govern the seminarians to habit a particular way of life. Its objective is committed to helping seminarians attain the desired growth and integration in their human, spiritual, intellectual, and pastoral formation.¹¹

Thesis Statement

By applying Jordan Peterson's pragmatic psychology to BF Skinner's operant conditioning and Viktor Frankl's logotherapy, the seminarians' free will and determining seminary structure will reconcile.

¹⁰ "Seminary," Cambridge Dictionary, accessed on April 23, 2024, <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/us/dictionary/english/seminary>.

¹¹ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors' Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 9.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

History

The idea of determinism started already during ancient times. It is important to know the history of the problem so that the researcher can differentiate what kind of determinism he is referring to. And so, the researcher will understand that kinds of determinism can't be used interchangeably. Below is a glimpse of the history of determinism and free will.

For Plato, free will is not caused by desire because desire is triggered by external factors; instead, being free is making oneself virtuous.¹² Aristotle then shares with Plato a concern for cultivating virtues through a repeated action called habit.”¹³

However, the debate starts during the Hellenistic period, when the idea of causal determinism arises. Causal determinism means that human actions are determined by preceding events. On the one hand, for instance, the Stoics:

They “were determinists insofar as they maintained that every state or event is necessitated by prior causes; but, at the same time, they were compatibilists since they were willing to defend the thesis that prior necessitation does not make impossible that we deserve praise or blame for the actions we perform. So, against the so-called “hard determinists,” the Stoics are intent on proving that, despite determinism, humans are genuinely responsible for their actions.”¹⁴

One of the examples of prior causes that the Stoics meant was the environmental factor, such as the rainy weather. It hinders the person from doing anything else; however, Stoics believed

¹² Hecht, Jonathan, *Freedom of the Will in Plato and Augustine* (British Journal for the History of Philosophy, 2014), 22: 196–216.

¹³ O'Connor, et al., "Free Will," The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, accessed on April 15, 2024, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/freewill/#toc>.

¹⁴ Ricardo Salles, “The Stoics on determinism and compatibilism,” Bryn Mawr Classical Review, accessed on April 15, 2024. <https://bmcr.brynmawr.edu/2007/2007.03.02/#:~:text=The%20Stoics%20were%20determinists%20insofar,for%20the%20actions%20we%20perform.>

that despite a determining weather, man is still responsible for the result of his action. If a man stays in his house instead of getting an umbrella and going to the market to buy groceries. Then the result of starvation is not caused by rain but by man's decision.

Similarly, Epicureans are kind of compatibilists because they believe that man consists of atoms and the movement of atoms causes man's actions. However, it denied the hard determinist approach because sometimes atoms depart from the usual movement.

They “had a more mechanistic conception of bodily action than the Stoics. They held that all things (human soul included) are constituted by atoms, whose law-governed behavior fixes the behavior of everything made of such atoms. But they rejected determinism by supposing that atoms, though law-governed, are susceptible to slight swerves’ or departures from the usual paths.”¹⁵

Skeptics, on the other hand, are hard determinists. They deny moral responsibility because they believe that human actions are caused by factors beyond their control.¹⁶ That is why, despite the effort that a man has made, he still doesn't deserve the reward since the effort was beyond man's control. Or a man cannot be punished because the sin committed is beyond his control.

Moving on, the medieval period shifted the idea of causal determinism to theological determinism, which means “the view that God determines every event that occurs in the history of the world.”¹⁷ This means that God foreknows everything and what He knows must happen. St. Augustine, for instance, said, 'God has already been made in the beginning of the foundation for some reason, for which people will be saved, who will be subject to eternal punishment.'¹⁸ Thus,

¹⁵ Connor, “Free Will.”

¹⁶ Gregg Caruso, Elizabeth Shaw, and Derk Pereboom. “Free Will Skepticism in Law and Society: An Overview.” Chapter. In *Free Will Skepticism in Law and Society: Challenging Retributive Justice*, ed. Elizabeth Shaw, Derk Pereboom, and Gregg D. Caruso (Cambridge University Press, 2019). 1–26

¹⁷ Chase B. Wrenn, “Naturalistic Epistemology,” *The Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, accessed on April 15, 2024, <https://iep.utm.edu/theological-determinism/>.

¹⁸ Wrenn, “Naturalistic Epistemology.”

entails that, as God foreknows the future in a way of knowing the path you proceed on (either in hell or heaven), then automatically God determines your action.

After 1,400 A.D., the modern age came into being, and one of the prominent philosophers there was René Descartes. He “identified freedom with actions that are not predetermined, even by the existence of divine foreknowledge.”¹⁹ It is because he believes that thinking is indubitable. However, “though he held that God has no cause other than himself (by saying, “I think, therefore I am ”), Descartes thought that everything apart from God is externally caused; he was a determinist concerning the created universe.”²⁰ Descartes believes that there are two substances in this world: the mind and matter. Mind is free, while matter is a mechanical being that acts limitedly based on an assigned function. “For him, the physical world was a deterministic machine, but our ideas and thoughts could be free (undetermined) and could change things in the material world (through the pineal gland in the brain, he thought).”²¹ Though the physical world can cause our actions, still man has his free will because man is not in the physical world, man or self is in mind.

After years, Nietzsche gives new ideas aside from theological and causal determinism. The term is psychological determinism, which means “the general position that psychological phenomena, including behaviors, are fixed, resulting from physical and other factors outside the control of the person.”²² For example, law, religion, policies, rules, etc. As long as it affects the behavior of someone. In the case of Nietzsche, he neglects religion or any philosophical moral theory, in the sense that it must not control the will of man. Rather, he implies that man is free and

¹⁹ Bob Doyle, “Rene Descartes,” The Information Philosopher, accessed on April 15, 2024, <https://www.informationphilosopher.com/solutions/philosophers/descartes/>.

²⁰ Vere Chappell, “Descartes’s compatibilism,” Philpapers, <https://philpapers.org/rec/CHADC-2#:~:text=And%20though%20he%20held%20that,respect%20to%20the%20created%20universe.>

²¹ Doyle, “Rene Descartes.”

²² “Psychological Determinism,” American Psychological Association, accessed on April 15, 2024, <https://dictionary.apa.org/psychological-determinism>.

has the will to power. “It is a basic drive found in everyone, but one that expresses itself in many different ways”²³ without being determined by government, religion, and other external factors that shape morality.

The history entails that there are four kinds of determinism. The causal determinism, theological determinism, logical determinism, and psychological determinism. The researcher intends to use the determinism of the contemporary era, which is psychological determinism. Despite being ancient, Plato and Aristotle’s ideas of free will can be part of psychological determinism. They are the foundation of philosophy, and both highlight the importance of mending free will and determinism. Their idea of discipline entails that determining someone is necessary since sometimes our desire is in ill form and needs a guide towards a good life.

Speaking about the good life, two of those who dominated in the contemporary era were BF Skinner and Victor Frankl. For BF Skinner, it is by determining someone with the help of rules that man obtains a good life, whereas for Viktor Frankl, it is by “will” where a man searches for meaning or it is through purpose where man can obtain a good life. Later, Jordan Peterson, a prominent psychologist, develops practical psychology that entails the importance of two.

BF Skinner’s on Psychological Determinism

“B.F. Skinner (born March 20, 1904, Susquehanna, Pennsylvania, U.S.—died August 18, 1990, Cambridge, Massachusetts) was an American psychologist and an influential exponent of behaviorism, which views behavior in terms of responses to environmental stimuli and favors the controlled, scientific study of responses as the most direct means of

²³ Emrys Westacott, “Nietzsche’s Concept of the Will to Power,” ThoughtCo, accessed on April 15, 2024, <https://www.thoughtco.com/nietzsches-concept-of-the-will-to-power-2670658>.

elucidating human nature.”²⁴ His behaviorism is called operant conditioning. It entails man’s behavior can be controlled through reinforcement applied.

But before that, as he earned an undergraduate degree, the period of his life then refers to a dark year. With that, he decided to become a writer, in which he wrote articles in newspapers. “While working as a clerk at a bookstore, Skinner happened upon the works of Pavlov and Watson (Skinner studies their behaviorism), which became a turning point in his life and career. Inspired by these works, B. F. Skinner decided to abandon his career as a novelist and entered the psychology graduate program at Harvard University.”²⁵ That’s a good thing because he is both a writer and a psychologist, which later on causes him to write a novel about his psychology.

As he became a doctor, he went back to the university as a professor. Moreover, he did experiments, which led him to his operant conditioning theory. BF Skinner did three experiments, namely positive reinforcement, negative reinforcement, and punishments. In his experiment, he used a rat and observed its response depending on the treatment the rat received. For positive reinforcement, Skinner treats the rat with a reward. There he observes that rewarding the rat causes it to simultaneously do the required behavior to receive again the reward given.

“Skinner used a hungry rat in a Skinner box to show how positive reinforcement works. The box contained a lever on the side, and as the rat moved about the box, it would accidentally knock the lever. Immediately after it did so, a food pellet would drop into a container next to the lever. The consequence of receiving food every time the rat hit the lever ensured that the animal repeated the action again and again.”²⁶

²⁴ “BF Skinner,” Britannica, accessed on April 17, 2024, <https://www.britannica.com/biography/B-F-Skinner>.

²⁵ Kendra Cherry, “B. F. Skinner’s Life, Theories, and Influence on Psychology,” Verywellmind, accessed on April 17, 2024, <https://www.verywellmind.com/b-f-skinner-biography-1904-1990-2795543#:~:text=While%20working%20as%20a%20clerk,graduate%20program%20at%20Harvard%20University.>

²⁶ Cyrus Wahome and Matt McMillin, “Operant Conditioning: What It Is and How It Works,” WebMD, accessed on April 17, 2024, <https://www.webmd.com/mental-health/what-is-operant-conditioning>.

For negative reinforcement, Skinner treats the rat by taking something from the rat, such as a convenient event or comfort.

“Skinner showed how negative reinforcement worked by placing a rat in his Skinner box and then subjecting it to an unpleasant electric current, which caused it some discomfort. As the rat moved about the box, it would accidentally knock the lever. Immediately it did, so the electric current would be switched off. The rats quickly learned to go straight to the lever after a few times of being put in the box. The consequence of escaping the electric current ensured that they would repeat the action again and again.”²⁷

For the punishment, BF Skinner defined it “as the opposite of reinforcement since it is designed to weaken or eliminate a response rather than increase it. It is an aversive event that decreases the behavior that it follows.”²⁸ It shows that there is a bad consequence in doing unrequired behavior. It develops fear in people, and so their behavior is limited.

With the experiments of BF Skinner, *Walden II* was written. It is a utopian novel in which Frazier (the character of the novel) tackles determining human behavior through operant conditioning. In the book, they use the term “behavioral engineering, behavioral science, or operant conditioning” instead of determinism. According to the novel,

The chief role of the behavioral sciences was to collect facts and insisted, possibly to reassure policymakers who might be alarmed by the ambitions of scientists, that “knowledge is no substitute for wisdom or common sense in making decisions.” Science would get the facts, but Congress or the President would make the decisions—with wisdom and common sense.²⁹

The story says that we don’t have free will because of controlling factors such as religion and the government. Plus, they give differences between scientists and political leaders. Though scientists initiate the change of behavior (for example, the problem of overpopulation, where they proposed the use of contraceptives), they are only doing experiments. Unlike political leaders, they are the decision-makers and planners. Combining the two, the people under their administration are trickly controlled. Though they feel convenient and liberated to do such things, for example,

²⁷ Saul McLeod, “Skinner-Operant Conditioning,” Simply Psychology, accessed on April 17, 2024, <https://hello.iitk.ac.in/sites/default/files/eng122a2021/resources/skinner%20operant%20conditioning.pdf>.

²⁸ McLeod, “Operant Conditioning.”

²⁹ BF Skinner, *Walden II* (Hackett Publishing Company, Inc., 2005), 3, b-ok, xyz.

having sex without impregnating. The truth is, they are not free at all. “Behavior could be changed by changing its consequences—that was operant conditioning.”³⁰

After *Walden II*, BF Skinner wrote more, one of which is entitled “Beyond Freedom and Dignity.” There, BF Skinner entails that the feeling of being free is just a product of reinforcement. The planners of society just make people believe that they are free, yet they are actually acting as planned and intended. BF Skinner said:

“It is hard to imagine a world in which people live together without quarreling, maintain themselves by producing the food, shelter, and clothing they need, enjoy themselves and contribute to the enjoyment of others in art, music, literature, and games, consume only a reasonable part of the resources of the world and add as little as possible to its pollution, bear no more children than can be raised decently, continue to explore the world around them and discover better ways of dealing with it, and come to know themselves accurately and, therefore, manage themselves effectively. Yet all this is possible, and even the slightest sign of progress should bring a kind of change that, in traditional terms, would be said to assuage wounded vanity, offset a sense of hopelessness or nostalgia, correct the impression that “we neither can nor need to do anything for ourselves,” and promote a “sense of freedom and dignity” by building “a sense of confidence and worth.” In other words, it should abundantly reinforce those who have been induced by their culture to work for its survival.”³¹

The book entails that man has the nature to strive in order to survive. Acknowledging that is also a creation of an ideal society where people’s behavior can be managed through fulfilling their basic needs to survive.

One more book from Skinner is entitled “Science and Human Behavior.” He showcases that determinism is “an individual displays certain behavior in certain states of probability.”³² What he meant about this was that behavior is attributed to the instinct or drive of any kind of being. And so, as a man triggers a drive, like, for example, the sexual drive, automatically, the man’s behavior is probably sexual. With that man’s drive, the planners know where to trigger or control their members.

³⁰ Skinner, *Walden*, 3.

³¹ BF Skinner, *Beyond Freedom and Dignity* (Hackett Publishing Company, Inc., 2002), 172, Z-library.

³² BF Skinner, *Science and Human Behavior* (Pearson Education, Inc., 2005), 156, Z-library.

Moreover, like BF Skinner, his co-behaviorist gave a wider meaning of determinism. However, determinism is used interchangeably with conditioning. If BF Skinner has the operant condition, Ivan Pavlov then has the classical conditioning in which “you are conditioned to associate particular object”³³ or your stimulus-response (S-R from hereon) is conditioned by something triggering. For example, a dog responds to the bell that was rung because the dog was conditioned that as the bell rang, there was food.

On top of that, Edward Thorndike's connectionism theory gave us an S-R framework. His theory entails that “associations or habits become strengthened or weakened by nature and the frequency of the S-R pairing. The model for S-R theory was trial and error learning in which certain responses came to be repeated more than others because of reward.”³⁴ S-R theory entails that because of reward, the stimulus within a man will respond, and repeatedly doing that becomes a man’s habit.

Similarly, John Watson believes in the S-R theory. In fact, having that theory causes him to claim that he can create a utopia if and only if he is given a dozen infants. He will condition depending on what he desires.

He “considered that humans are born with a few reflexes and the emotional reactions of love and rage. All other behavior is learned through S-R associations through conditioning. He believed in the power of conditioning so much that he said that if he is given a dozen healthy infants, he can make them into anything you want them to be, basically through making stimulus-response connections through conditioning.”³⁵

³³ Maria Rita D. Lucas and Brenda B. Corpuz, *Facilitating Learner-Centered Teaching, 5th Edition* (Lorimar Publishing Inc., 2020), 81.

³⁴ Lucas and Corpuz, *Facilitating*, 82.

³⁵ Lucas and Corpuz, *Facilitating*, 83.

Apart from that, neo-behaviorists like Albert Bandura define conditioning through modeling. Accordingly, “the observer is reinforced by a model.”³⁶ Then, the observer imitates the model, and the way he/she imitates affects his/her behavior.

Viktor Frankl on Free Will

Viktor Emil Frankl was born on March 26, 1905, and died on September 2, 1997. He was a Holocaust survivor during the Nazi concentration camp. By the time he entered there at the age of 37, he was already a psychiatrist and neurologist, specializing in the treatment of suicidal patients. But it is there in the camp that he developed his psychology theory called logotherapy (Greek for “healing through meaning”).³⁷ A theory that entails man has free will.

“Frankl viewed logotherapy as a way to enhance existing therapies by emphasizing the meaning-dimension or spiritual dimension of human beings.³⁸ This means that Frankl’s psychology is not limited only to man’s psychological and emotional issues but also the existential concerns. Three philosophical and psychological concepts make up Frankl’s logotherapy: freedom of will, will to meaning, and meaning of life. These three are defined by Dr. Mellisa Madeson.

“Freedom of will asserts that humans are free to decide and can take a stance toward both internal and external conditions. (Examples of internal conditions are man’s attitudes, values, search for meaning, and existential will.) (Then, examples of external conditions are laws, norms, other people, genetic predisposition, ‘treat of punishment’, etc.) Freedom in this context is defined as a space to shape one’s own life within limits of specific possibilities. It provides the client with room for autonomy in the face of somatic or psychological illness. In essence, we are free to choose our responses no matter our circumstances.

Will to meaning states that humans are free to achieve goals and purposes in life. Frustration, aggression, addiction, depression, and suicidality arise when individuals cannot realize their “will to meaning.” As humans, our primary motive is to search for meaning or purpose in our lives. We are capable of surpassing pleasure and supporting pain for a meaningful cause.

³⁶ Lucas and Corpuz, *Facilitating*, 96.

³⁷ Alex Vesely et al., “The Life of Viktor Frankl,” The Viktor E. Frankl Institute of America, accessed on April 21, 2024, <https://viktorfranklamerica.com/viktor-frankl-bio/>.

³⁸ Alexander Batthyany, “What is logotherapy/existential analysis?” Viktor Frankl Institute, accessed on April 21, 2024, <https://www.viktorfrankl.org/logotherapy.html>.

Meaning in life is based on the idea that meaning is an objective reality rather than merely an illusion or personal perception. Humans have both freedom and responsibility to bring forth their best possible selves by realizing the meaning of the moment in every situation.”³⁹

The three entail that man’s behavior is no constraint due to our search for meaning. Despite the presence of external factors such as norms and laws, man has the will to choose his response in any particular situation.

During the time Viktor Frankl was in a concentration camp, he wrote how he experienced the freedom of will, will to meaning, and meaning in life. In his book entitled “Man Search for Meaning,” he says.

“We who lived in concentration camps can remember the men who walked through the huts comforting others, giving away their last piece of bread. They may have been few in number, but they offer sufficient proof that everything can be taken from a man but one thing: the last of the human freedoms—to choose one's attitude in any given set of circumstances, to choose one's own way. And there were always choices to make. Every day, every hour, offered the opportunity to make a decision, a decision which determined whether you would or would not submit to those powers which threatened to rob you of your very self, your inner freedom, which determined whether or not you would become the plaything of circumstance, renouncing freedom and dignity to become molded into the form of the typical inmate... Even though conditions such as lack of sleep, insufficient food and various mental stresses may suggest that the inmates were bound to react in certain ways, in the final analysis it becomes clear that the sort of person the prisoner became was the result of an inner decision, and not the result of camp influences alone... therefore, any man can, even under such circumstances, decide what shall become of him—mentally and spiritually.”⁴⁰

So, despite the circumstances in life, we can choose to be and choose not to be. Moreover, there are commentaries on the work of Victor Frankl. For instance, Nathan Ketsdever (launcher and writer of the Compassion in Politics website) said that man has free will and “man is not fully conditioned and determined but rather he determines himself whether he gives in to conditions or

³⁹ Mellissa Madeson, “Logotherapy: Viktor Frankl’s Theory of Meaning,” Positive Psychology, accessed on April 21, 2024, <https://positivepsychology.com/viktor-frankl-logotherapy/#:~:text=Freedom%20of%20will%20asserts%20that,within%20limits%20of%20specific%20possibilities.>

⁴⁰ Viktor Frankl, *Man’s search for meaning* (Beacon Press, 1992), 75, Z-library.

stands up to them.”⁴¹ The reinforcement conditioned unto man is useless since the behavior depends on the choices of man, either give in or rebel.

Then, according also to Kennon Sheldon, a Curator’s Distinguished Professor in psychological sciences at the University of Missouri, it is important to believe that we have free will because “feeling autonomous and self-determined—that you have free will—is a basic psychological need, and satisfying this need is critical for your mental health.”⁴² So believe that man has free will. Though extrinsic motivation exists, such as the determined rules given by religion, government, etc., and it causes us to feel that our behavior is controlled, “losing your sense of free will, in this sense, might make your life much less enjoyable and interesting.”⁴³ So, believe you have free will, and you find happiness in life. It is pure happiness because it is through the search for meaning.

Plus, Sean P. Murray, a podcast host and writer, gives 5 lessons from Viktor Frankl’s book “Man’s Search for Meaning.”

First, we always retain the ability to choose our attitude, because no matter what life experiences we confront, we always have the inner freedom to decide our attitude and to remain true to our character and duty. Second, there will be suffering. It’s how we react to suffering that counts. Third, purpose has power. Fourth, the true test of our character is revealed in how we act... because each person must answer the question for themselves. We find our unique meaning based on our circumstances, our relationships, and our experiences. Life is essentially testing us, and the answer is revealed in how we respond. And lastly, human kindness can be found in the most surprising places. There are only two types of people: decent human beings and indecent human beings. Both can be found everywhere. They penetrate every group and every society. And Frankl occasionally experienced startling moments of human kindness from guards despite being terrible. Frankl recalls a time when a guard, at great risk to himself, secretly gave him a piece of bread.⁴⁴

⁴¹ “Victor Frankl Quote on Free Will and Determinism,” Compassion in Politics: Christian Social Entrepreneurship, Education Innovation, and Base of the Pyramid/BOP Solutions, accessed on April 21, 2024, <https://compassioninpolitics.wordpress.com/2012/02/24/victor-frankl-quote-on-free-will-and-determinism/>.

⁴² Kennon Sheldon, “The three reasons why it’s good for you to believe in free will,” Psyche, accessed on April 21, 2024, <https://psyche.co/ideas/the-three-reasons-why-its-good-for-you-to-believe-in-free-will>.

⁴³ Sheldon, “free will.”

⁴⁴ Sean P. Murray, “5 Lessons from Viktor Frankl’s book “Man’s Search for Meaning,” Real Time Performance, accessed on April 21, 2024, <https://www.realtimetype.com/5-lessons-from-viktor-frankls-book-mans-search-for-meaning/>.

The five entail that the primary source of the behavior is within man's desire for meaning, not of external factors. Moreover, free will and freedom can't be used interchangeably. According to the Viktor Frankl Institute of Logotherapy in Israel,

“When Frankl outlines his three principles of logotherapy, the phrase he uses is “freedom of will” and not “freedom of choice.” It is true that Frankl enjoys playing with language. Using the word “will” for all three principles creates an elegant construct. But there is a deeper reason. In his discussion of freedom, Frankl elaborates on examples where a person is free to choose his attitude towards his instincts or towards what is happening. Why does he focus on attitude more than actions? To choose a certain behavior requires freedom of movement. But what makes you decide to choose that course of action in the first place? You must have been capable of choosing what you think about what is happening. No one can dictate to you what to do, and no one can dictate to you what you should want to do. Your “will” is free. What is very interesting about “will” is that there is a spectrum from “little wants,” such as which flavor of ice cream you prefer, to “big wants” that relate to your core convictions, your mission statement, and that which emanates from your sensed purpose in life. Your “will” being free, you are capable of deciding to forgo your little wants in favor of your big wants. Recognizing the presence of a higher value, you can do without the ice cream. Maybe it will be harmful to your health. Maybe someone else is hungrier than you. The ultimate source of our will is our autonomous essence as what Frankl calls “deciding beings.”⁴⁵

So that is the difference between the two. Freedom is a choice without undue constraints imposed by external forces, such as government, society, rules, norms, etc. But free will is a search for meaning even if there is a lack of freedom. This is in the sense that even though man can't control the situation, he is still free to find meaning or purpose in life.

Note: On the last page of the St. John XXIII Seminary Rule of Life, they use the word freedom rather than free will.

Jordan Peterson

Dr. Jordan B. Peterson is a psychologist, online educator (YouTube and podcast), professor Emeritus at the University of Toronto, and a book author. “He has written three books, *Maps of Meaning*, an academic work presenting a new scientifically grounded theory of religious and

⁴⁵ “Freedom of Will,” Viktor Frankl Institute of Logotherapy in Israel, accessed on April 21, 2024, <https://themeaningseeker.org/freedom-of-will/>.

political belief, the bestselling *12 Rules for Life*, and *Beyond Order*, which have sold more than seven million copies.”⁴⁶

His book entitled *12 Rules of Life* entails guidelines for life to achieve a meaningful life. In fact, according to Jordan Peterson, “We require rules, standards, and values—alone and together. We’re pack animals, beasts of burden. We must bear a load to justify our miserable existence. We require routine and tradition. That’s order.”⁴⁷ The twelve rules are these:

- RULE 1: Stand up straight with your shoulders back.
- RULE 2: Treat yourself like someone you are responsible for helping.
- RULE 3: Make friends with people who want the best for you.
- RULE 4: Compare yourself to who you were yesterday, not to who someone else is today.
- RULE 5: Do not let your children do anything that makes you dislike them.
- RULE 6: Set your house in perfect order before you criticize the world.
- RULE 7: Pursue what is meaningful (not what is expedient).
- RULE 8: Tell the truth—or, at least, don’t lie.
- RULE 9: Assume that the person you are listening to might know something you don’t.
- RULE 10: Be precise in your speech.
- RULE 11: Do not bother children when they are skateboarding.
- Rule 12: Pet a cat when you encounter one on the street.

These 12 rules condition the reader to do so, but the rules are not a hindrance to free will. In fact, according to Dr. Norman D. Doidge, MD, a friend of Peterson and who wrote the foreword of the *12 Rules for Life*, he said:

“Sometimes these rules are demanding. They require you to undertake an incremental process over time, stretching you to a new limit. That requires, as I’ve said, venturing into the unknown. Stretching yourself beyond the boundaries of your current self requires carefully choosing and then pursuing ideals: ideals that are up there, above you, superior to you... but rules remind us that without it we quickly become slaves to our passions—and there’s nothing freeing about that.”⁴⁸

Thus, Jordan Peterson's rules are not a behavior controller but a discipline that leads people to a better life. It is a guiding star towards man's search for meaning. Moreover, according to

⁴⁶“Jordan B. Peterson,” Jordan B. Peterson, accessed on April 21, 2024, <https://www.jordanbpeterson.com/about/>.

⁴⁷ Jordan B. Peterson, *12 Rules for Life* (Random House Canada, 2018), Table of Contents, Z-Library.

⁴⁸ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, Foreword.

Saniya Ahmad Khan, 12 rules for life lead us to a virtuous life in which we have freer behavior rather than being in vices. And so, these are the virtues that the 12 Rules for Life help:

Promote self-awareness

Peterson's rules encourage individuals to reflect on their actions, attitudes, and responsibilities, fostering greater self-awareness and personal growth.

Facilitate resilience

By advocating for principles like standing tall and taking responsibility, Peterson's rules empower individuals to face life's challenges with resilience and fortitude.

Enhance relationships

Rules such as making friends with those who support your well-being and treating children respectfully can strengthen interpersonal relationships and foster healthier connections.

Foster moral integrity

Peterson's emphasis on truthfulness, responsibility, and meaningful pursuits promotes moral integrity and ethical behavior, contributing to a more virtuous society.

Provide direction

Each rule offers practical guidance for navigating life's complexities, providing individuals with a roadmap for personal development and fulfillment. In conclusion, Jordan Peterson's 12 Rules for Life offers valuable insights and practical wisdom for individuals seeking to lead more meaningful and fulfilling lives. By embracing these principles, we can cultivate resilience, foster healthier relationships, and pursue greater personal growth and fulfillment.⁴⁹

Other than 12 Rules for Life, Jordan Peterson does have videos on YouTube telling the audience that it is fine to choose being determined. Though he is fast in speech, his videos still have points. One of the videos of Peterson is entitled "Jordan Peterson Explains Free Will." In the video, an interviewer asked him, "Does man have free will? Then Peterson answered that we have free will for we can achieve a desired end; however, our will is immature because of our short vision towards possibility, and so we integrate possibility with culture.

What do you confront when you wake up in the morning? Well, it's not the damn furniture in your room; it's the possibility of the day. Know the possibility of the day. Makes itself manifest to you and it presents itself as a problem how will I interact with what's transforming in front of me in a manner that will bring about the desired end you might be very bad at that which just means you're impulsive and after very after the realization of very short-term visions and so you're sophisticated and you integrate the possibility that makes itself manifest to you with a higher order and sophisticated vision and then you grapple or wrestle with that emergent possibility to realize it and by doing that you participate in the creation of the world and the fact that you're of that kind is the reason for example that our culture is predicated on the idea that you're

⁴⁹ Saniya Ahmad Khan, "Jordan Peterson's wisdom: 12 Rules for life explained," Your Story, April 4, 2024, <https://yourstory.com/2024/04/jordan-peterson-12-rules-guide>.

made in the image of God because God is the spirit that confronts chaos and possibility and transforms it into habitable reality and that's you in the microcosm and that's a Divine thing that you're participating in and you can tell that because if you do it right it's deeply meaningful and you can tell that because if you do it right and it's deeply meaningful the habitable order that you generate from the encounter with chaos and potential is good"⁵⁰

The next video is entitled "Your Ethics Determine Your Success." It's an eight-minute video and to summarize it, it entails that we must have ethics in life. There are instances when we belong to such institutions as workplaces, seminaries, etc. and it feels like we want to go out because that is a bad place anymore. The boss is a tyrant, low salary, etc. But Peterson said, "almost everywhere, and this certainly has been the case."⁵¹ He adds, "Virtually, I've gone above and beyond the call of duty you know and wake in an intelligent way, interpersonally socially with regards to the diligence of your work with regards to the truth of your attitude and your courage and all of that."⁵² Thus, success is not by quitting but by allowing ethics to determine your behavior. Because wherever you go, no place does not require you to try. Even a small job requires a tedious demand, but despite that, success is still achievable. And so, "it's ethics that determines success in a functional society. It's ethics that determine it's a bloody lie."⁵³

It is also tackled in the video the chance of choosing the other way around if at times our effort does not gain success but abuse. ⁵⁴ Thus, man is still free since he can choose. But note that the decision is ethical since we cannot live statically in tyranny. Ethics means a reconciliation of determinism and free will.

⁵⁰ Jordan B. Peterson, "Jordan Peterson Explains Free Will," Jordan B. Peterson Clips, posted on January 26, 2024, YouTube Video, 4: 58, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hdENDumGiWw>.

⁵¹ Jordan B. Peterson, "Your Ethics Determine Your Success," Jordan B. Peterson Clips, posted on July 18, 2022, YouTube Video, 3: 02, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CMi5TU6d93w>.

⁵² Peterson, "Your Ethics Determine Your Success," 3: 10.

⁵³ Peterson, "Your Ethics Determine Your Success," 3: 39.

⁵⁴ Peterson, "Your Ethics Determine Your Success," 3: 21.

The next one is entitled “You’re Led by Your Values.” In a YouTube video, Jordan Peterson said:

“You're a deterministic entity precisely. So, it's like you can participate in the construction of a value system, but you know you have to take your biological nature into the mind, you have to take your cultural nature into mind, and you have to take other people into mind, and so you know, you have, you can vary the game, but I don't think you can really change the rules.”⁵⁵

This lecture is in line with Nietzsche’s Übermensch, which talks about no ultimate meaning but to create your own. However, Peterson believed like Heidegger that “value was something that manifested itself in the world and attracted your attention.”⁵⁶ In other words, rules are important for our being in the world, and without the world, we cannot define that man is there. Then, as man is there in the world, rules are also in him and for him.

In connection, the fourth video is entitled “Importance of being ethical.” Peterson wants to emphasize that whether man knows or doesn’t know, our culture influences our actions. But a necessary submission because we need a standard of how to live. He said:

“You have an ethical responsibility to act in that light, and you might claim not to believe that, but I would say your whole culture is predicated on that belief. And in so far as you are an active member of that culture and a believer in its structure, then you believe it. You might not be very good at believing it; you might be full of conflict and doubt, and you might not be able to articulate it, but it's still right.”⁵⁷

⁵⁵ Jordan B. Peterson, “You’re Led by Your Values,” The Bests, posted on September 23, 2020, YouTube Video, 5:38, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ysXAvNb_zbo&t=92s.

⁵⁶ Peterson, “You’re Led by Your Values,” 5:24.

⁵⁷ Jordan B. Peterson, “Importance of Being Ethical by Jordan Peterson,” Inner Pigment, posted on December 23, 2022, YouTube Video, 9: 10, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qGoSMrBaYLI&t=4s>.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This paper makes use of a conceptual research method which utilizes abstract concepts and ideas. It relies on the researcher analyzing available information on a given topic. It focuses on the concepts and theories that can be used to explain the issue being studied. The method uses existing concepts and theories to establish the validity of the current issue trying to be solved.

By using this method, the researcher gathers and examines data related to BF Skinner's operant conditioning, Viktor Frankl's logotherapy, and Jordan Peterson's practical psychology. This results in a deeper understanding of seminarians' true nature of their vocation. Then the study will put together the ideas of BF Skinner (determinism) and Viktor Frankl (free will) who are diametrically opposites using Jordan Peterson's balance of chaos and order to shed light on the tension. Lastly, the insights of BF Skinner, Viktor Frankl and Jordan Peterson, will illustrate the co-existence of determinism and free will in the context of seminary formation, addressing seminary rule of life and seminarians free will can be a mended rift.

Argument Design

The study aims to explore the interplay of determinism and free will in the context of seminary formation. Hence, the researcher uses a converging argument design. A convergent argument is a type of argument that entails that the resolution is supported by two (or more) claims, which one cannot support the resolution alone but collectively so. Moreover, the paper will follow the compatibility claim of Skinner's Determinism and Frankl's Freedom. Then, through the use of

a convergence argument presentation, the idea of J. Peterson will serve as the focal point for these two assertions.

Presentation of Argument

In exploring the interplay of determinism and free will, the researcher distinguishes the differences between the two. Determinism is defined through BF Skinner's operant conditioning or psychological determinism, while free will is defined through Viktor Frankl's logotherapy. Moreover, aside from differentiating the two, the researcher also combines them using Jordan Peterson's practical psychology. Using these three claims, the researcher identifies the meaning of each term. Then, explain its necessity for seminary formation. Lastly, know the relevance of making the two dependents on each other.

CHAPTER 4

PRESENTATION OF DATA AND DISCUSSION OF ARGUMENTS

1. Free Will and Determinism

a. Then and Now

The debates between determinism and free will already started a long time ago. Questioning if man has free will, then no one determines him; if man was determined, then he doesn't have free will. An old philosophical issue, yet it has profound implications even for the present generation. In particular in the seminary formation.

There are four types of determinism, namely, causal or physical determinism, theological determinism, logical determinism, and psychological determinism. The oldest among the four was physical and theological determinism. Physical determinism means the laws of nature determine us,⁵⁸ and theological determinism means God determines us.⁵⁹ The remaining two are offspring of the modern and contemporary eras. Logical determinism means we are determined by one and only possibility,⁶⁰ while psychological determinism means laws and policies determine our behavior.⁶¹

In the context of seminary formation, the evident type of determinism that exists is psychological determinism, where the presence of the seminary rule of life seemingly entails that it controls the seminarians' behavior. Specifically, by following it and avoiding messing with it due to the punishment that consequence.

⁵⁸ JR Lucas, "Types of Determinism," Oxford Scholar Online, September 1970, <https://academic.oup.com/book/12161/chapter-abstract/161577125?redirectedFrom=fulltext>.

⁵⁹ Lucas, "Types of Determinism."

⁶⁰ Lucas, "Types of Determinism,"

⁶¹ Lucas, "Types of Determinism,"

On the contrary, seminarians as rational beings indicate they control their action. Thus, they have free will. However, the researcher does not seek winners of this debate but a philosophical analysis if there is an interplay between the two. Specifically, using the idea of Jordan Peterson, reconciling BF Skinner and Viktor Frankl.

b. BF Skinner's Determinism and the Seminary Rule of Life

Psychological Determinism submits that man's behavior is secretly manipulated by a design such as laws and policies. It controls behavior because of the presence of reinforcement, where if man follows laws thoroughly, then he gains reward while doing the opposite gains punishment. One of the prominent people who influenced psychological determinism to exist was BF Skinner. He has a theory named Operant Conditioning, a behavior modifier through reward and punishment. In his book *Walden II*, he stated that there are 4 roles in society: the scientist, the planner, the manager, and the worker.⁶²

The scientist conducts long-term experiments on human behavior and then creates a design that could control it. Within the design are the three reinforcements, namely, positive reinforcement, negative reinforcement, and punishment. Positive reinforcement is rewarding so that you follow the design. Negative reinforcement is taking something from you for you to follow the design. Lastly, punishment is inflicting pain for you not to disobey the design. After that, this design will be transferred to the planner, who will oversee and ensure that the design is effectively practiced. The role of managers then is to oversee specific areas. The workers, on the other hand, are the people who follow the guidelines established by the planners and managers. They typically engage in various tasks as assigned and are victims of reinforcement.

⁶² Skinner, *Walden*, 53.

In the context of a seminary, like Walden II, the seminary also has the scientist, planner, manager, and worker. The scientists are the Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors' Board. They created a design named Seminary Rule of Life; it is a set of guidelines that governs the seminarian to customize a particular behavior. The planner is the rector who oversees the seminarian and is responsible for rewarding and punishing. The managers, on the other hand, are the rest of the formators. They handle a specific area of formation. For example, the dean of studies focuses on the academic life of the seminarians, while the spiritual director focuses on the prayer life of the seminarians. Lastly, the workers are the seminarians. They engage in various tasks implemented by the planner and managers. Plus, they are victims of reinforcement due to the psychological effects of reward and punishment stated in the Seminary Rule of Life.

Seminary Rule of Life Section 4 Paragraph B entails punishment. Seminarians are bound to disciplinary action if they do not follow the guidelines. It says, "The formators determine if the seminarian under disciplinary action should be sent home or render due recompense inside the seminary."⁶³ Thus, seminarians must do the schedules whether they like it or not. Seminarians will study philosophy even if they find themselves good in engineering or nursing. Seminarians will do *laborandum* even without being paid. And it is due to the punishment if they don't. In other words, seminarians are psychologically determined.

c. Viktor Frankl's Free Will and the Seminarians

In contrast to BF Skinner's psychological determinism, Viktor Frankl offers a view that emphasizes human free will. Viktor Frankl is a psychiatrist and a Holocaust survivor of the Nazi Concentration camp in World War II. There he developed logotherapy, a form of existential

⁶³ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors' Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 26.

analysis that implicates the primary human drive is the search for meaning, not the reward and punishment inflicted by a planner. According to Frankl, even in the most deterministic of circumstances, such as in a concentration camp, individuals retain the freedom to choose their attitude and find meaning in their suffering.⁶⁴

Upon arriving at the concentration camp, Viktor Frankl's possession was taken away. Even his family, degree, and name. Everything was lost, and they just replaced it with a number tattooed on his arm, which served as his identity. Then, in the following days, he experiences more cruelty. The prisoners are subjected to dehumanization. They were starved, given inconvenient shelter, given little clothes, and they were forced into hard labor in exchange only for cigarettes, not food. Having that circumstance, those who can't do the labor anymore will be sentenced to death. Thus, they have to do it because the punishment is so fearsome. Plus, there are selection moments. Those who are healthy will have the chance to live, while those who are ill, old, have low weight, and are incapable of working are brought to other areas and put into a gas chamber that releases a deadly poison that kills them. Seemingly, they have no freedom since, whether they like it or not, they are all subject to death. Even if they do the hard work, because of starvation, prisoners decrease their weight and become subject to gas chambers.

However, even in the face of overwhelming despair, Viktor Frankl observes something about the human spirit. He finds out that one can survive the situation, not because of physical well-being but psychologically. He realized that those who managed to find meaning even in a very dark circumstance often have the purpose to do something. For some, this meaning is found

⁶⁴ Frankl, *Man's search for meaning*, 139.

through the desire to be reunited with their loved ones; it could also be a sense of duty, religious belief, or the ambition to be notable.

Viktor Frankl, on the other hand, finds meaning through the hope of seeing his wife (though he did not know that she had already perished).⁶⁵ And because of that, he chooses to obey the requirements of the camp. He did the labor for him not to be subject to death. Then he conquers starvation by exchanging his gained cigarettes for food.⁶⁶ Plus, during the selection moment, Viktor Frankl added layers of clothing to his uniform so that he would appear strong and healthier.⁶⁷ These acts help Frankl not to be punished but note that he was not determined by the punishment, but it is his will fortified by the sense of purpose.

Hence, man has free will. Though rewards and punishments occur, remember that the primary drive of human behavior is the search for meaning or a sense of purpose. In the seminary context, though the presence of the rule of life inflicts reward and punishment, it does not hinder the seminarian from doing what their hearts desire.

Some of the questions of the interview before entering the seminary were, “Why are you here? Or what’s your purpose? Why apply to this kind of institution?” Commonly, the accepted applicants are those who answered, “I want to become a priest” (some say in different forms yet have the same intent). And so, they passed and became seminarians. It is their “I” that drives their behavior.

Furthermore, seminarians are responsible for their actions. They still have the ability to choose what attitudes to apply in such situations, depending on purpose. Since a seminarian has

⁶⁵ Frankl, *Man's search for meaning*, 49.

⁶⁶ Frankl, *Man's search for meaning*, 21.

⁶⁷ Frankl, *Man's search for meaning*, 25.

the purpose of becoming a priest in the future, he does what the seminary rule of life says because, through it, he can find meaning in life. On the contrary, the seminarian who loses his purpose to become a priest can choose not to do the seminary rule of life and allow himself to be the subject of Section 4 paragraph 4. Like a prisoner in the Nazi camp who loses the purpose of life, allowing himself to be subject to a gas chamber.

d. Jordan Peterson and the Interplay of Free Will and Determinism in the Seminary Context

The issue between BF Skinner's determinism and Viktor Frankl's free will can be understood through Jordan Peterson's pragmatic psychology. Jordan Peterson, a contemporary psychologist, mends the rift between determinism and free will by stressing the interplay between order and chaos in human existence. In his book *12 Rules for Life*, he wrote in his overture that order is a determining factor like social norms—a structure that guides life.⁶⁸ Whereas chaos is an unexpected event, which entails possibilities, growth, and adventure.⁶⁹ This interplay suggests that, through chaos, humans can still make choices among the unexpected possibilities while still within a structure that can serve as their guide throughout their adventure. Thus, a reconciliation that compliments both determinism and free will.

The balance between order and chaos is also the balance of BF Skinner and Viktor Frankl. Jordan Peterson mentioned these psychologists in his book as an important person to believe in. BF Skinner's operant conditioning is referred to because Jordan Peterson believes in the importance of discipline.⁷⁰ Then Viktor Frankl was mentioned because of the need for authentic

⁶⁸ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 22.

⁶⁹ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 22.

⁷⁰ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 148.

living in our search for meaning.⁷¹ Combining the two creates harmony, where authentic living can be guided by discipline.

Same also in the seminary context; there is harmony of order and chaos within. This insight suggests that while seminarians are influenced by the seminary rule of life, they still possess the capacity to exercise their free will. This is in a sense of responsibility. In fact, there are many designs in society that will determine human behavior. And among the many, a man's free will can prefer what design will determine him.

A seminarian has many options in life. In some cases, they are free to go out and prefer other designs. They can choose to be enslaved by peer pressure, unguided personal desires, etc. But in the case of remaining or choosing the seminary, the seminarians choose to be determined by the rule of life. Choosing something that could discipline his character under what his heart desires, which is to be a priest. This approach (harmony of chaos and order) encourages seminarians to face the challenges and uncertainties of life with might and integrity, thus actively participating in the seminary formation rather than passively accepting it.

2. Peterson's 12 Rules for Life: A Reconciliation of Two Opposite Concepts (Determinism and Free Will)

Jordan Peterson gives the "12 rules for life." Rules as a determiner yet encouraging man to be free. In fact, the foreword of his book highlights the importance of rules as a guide because, without them, we just become slaves of our ill passions.⁷² To support this, Plato and Aristotle highlight the

⁷¹ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 227.

⁷² Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 125.

importance of discipline. One must undergo discipline because man's free will is still immature.⁷³ Below, each rule will be discussed, as well as showing how Peterson's concept connects the two opposite concepts (determinism and free will).

a. Rule number 1: Stand Up Straight with Your Shoulders Back

The word "stand up straight with your shoulders back" is not just a posture but a metaphor for leadership. Then note that the essence of priesthood is leadership. RFIS states that "the order of bishops and priests is inseparably part of the ecclesial community and, at the same time, by the will of Christ and in continuance of the work of the Apostles, have been constituted to be pastors and leaders."⁷⁴ Plus, the seminary vision is to form the seminarian after the mind and heart of Jesus Christ.⁷⁵ Since Jesus is a high priest (a leader), a seminarian must be a leader too.

Jordan Peterson encourages people to be alphas through competition. Competition is natural to society. It is necessary so that we can improve the quality of life. Like a lobster in Peterson's example, the lobster competes for a territory so that catching food will be convenient for it.⁷⁶ However, animal competition is different from human competition (see rule no. 4). A man's opponent is his past self. He needs to conquer his old self so that he can increase his serotonin.⁷⁷ This serotonin helps build confidence (one of the attributes of a leader).

With that, it seems like a determinist point of view. The rule showcases societal conditioning on behavior, suggesting that leadership is an external influence or a norm. However, adopting

⁷³ Hecht, Jonathan, *Freedom of the Will in Plato and Augustine* (British Journal for the History of Philosophy, 2014), 22: 196–216.

⁷⁴ Congregation for the Clergy, *Ratio Fundamentalis Institutionis Sacerdotalis* (L'OSSERVATORE ROMANO VATICAN CITY, 2016), 18.

⁷⁵ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors' Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 8.

⁷⁶ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 34.

⁷⁷ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 36.

leadership can also be a conscious choice that needs inner strength or might. Though a seminarian is required to be a leader (structured by the rule of life through human formation and pastoral formation), it is his desire to be a priest that causes the need for leadership. A seminarian who leads accepts the profound responsibility that comes with priesthood. However, this desire is unachievable without the guidance of the seminary rule of life.

b. Rule number 2: Treat Yourself Like Someone You Are Responsible for Helping

Rule number 2 highlights the need for individuals to take responsibility for their own lives. It is due to the fact that man is vulnerable. Man can feel pain, self-disgust, shame, horror, etc. Same also with the seminarians; they are also vulnerable since they are still humans. Hence, the seminary creates the objective that St. John XXIII College Seminary is committed to helping the seminarians attain the desired growth and integration of their human, spiritual, intellectual, and pastoral formation.⁷⁸ These 4 pillars of formation have specific programs that shape the seminarians' behavior in particular to their lifestyle, virtues, and values. In connection with BF Skinner, his perspective would emphasize the importance of creating an environment that has reinforcement in taking care of the vulnerability of oneself.

Moreover, the topic of helping oneself is also a critical aspect of one's existential responsibility. It recognizes the power of free will, particularly in choosing one's attitude towards vulnerability. This underscores Frankl's search for meaning since taking care of the self can be a primary purpose in life.

Now, how did determinism and free will get reconciled? Peterson emphasizes to consider the future and think. Allow the "self" to create questions and reflect about decisions to make. And one

⁷⁸ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors' Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 9.

of the decisions to make is to know where you are going.⁷⁹ What design can be appropriate in treating myself? What is something that helps me grow? Since man is vulnerable, he needs a design that can be a scaffold for building the best version of himself. And so, the seminary rule of life fits the role of scaffolding, aiding the seminarians to grow in life. Seminarians' free will will choose a design that will determine their growth. A reflective choice that allows the consequence of determinism.

c. Rule number 3: Make Friends with People Who Want the Best for You

In this rule, Jordan Peterson advocates for the importance of surrounding oneself with people who can attract our personalities. That the people we choose to associate with can affect our growth and not our fall.⁸⁰ Then this kind of life shows a determinism approach because the moment we often spend time with people, we likely adopt their traits and behaviors. Depending on who our friend is. Peterson states that if we choose a friend who wants the best for us, they are likely to encourage us to do good and won't tolerate us for our cynical attitudes.⁸¹ In fact, they punish us to resolve the proper behavior a man should act. In case of being belong to the wrong person, they encourage you to be what they want. They get jealous of you in times of achievement and withdraw their friendship or punish you for your achievement.⁸²

Same also with the seminary formation. Seminarians automatically belonged to the community (a group of people or a co-seminarian). In fact, seminary vision indicates to form young college seminarians... as a family of basic ecclesial community.⁸³ As the seminarian belongs to the

⁷⁹ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 86.

⁸⁰ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 104.

⁸¹ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 104.

⁸² Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 104.

⁸³ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors' Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 8.

community, he is then determined by the traits and behaviors of those people, but what is good about being in a community of seminarians is that they share the same dream in which to become priests in the future. There might be instances in which a co-seminarian encourages his brother to study, pray, play, etc., or scold others for not following the seminary rule of life. This might be a determining factor; however, this happened because of a shared will or purpose. Shaping each other, doing something in the present to achieve the same goal in the future.

With that, it again shows a reconciliation of free will and determinism. The primary source of behavior is the purpose of becoming a priest, but one can't deny the power of determinism in a community setting.

d. Rule number 4: Compare Yourself to Who You Were Yesterday, Not to Who Someone Else Today.

Within the seminary, there resides a standard. For example, in the academic aspect, first-year seminarians are expected to have a general average grade of 2.25 or higher, while second-year to fourth-year seminarians are required to have a general average of higher than 2.00.⁸⁴ Since within a community are seminarians with different levels of IQ, instances might turn into competition. Some can be gifted and become advantageous in that aspect, while others will find it hard to achieve a specific standard. Sometimes, some seminarians might feel envious and try something destructive to someone who's on top or cheat to level up. Fortunately, the seminary inhabits the common good.⁸⁵ It encourages the seminarian not to make his co-seminarian an

⁸⁴ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors' Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 23.

⁸⁵ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors' Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 39.

opponent but a healthy inspiration. One of the practices of the common good in the seminary is disciplining everyone to study with each other so that no one is left behind.

Somehow similar to Peterson's rule number 4. Shaping people not to compare themselves to others but instead compare themselves to their vulnerable past. The main goal of the seminary rule of life (specifically, intellectual formation) is not to make the seminarians compete but to enhance the academic growth of each seminarian.⁸⁶ However, discipline can't be possible without the "pay attention" mode. Peterson is saying that one must focus on the importance of one's journey.⁸⁷ Focus as in trying to contemplate or asking questions. Assessing the self of its real purpose—why we seek growth—and assessing the self of what things to do to achieve such purpose. Even though one is unskilled at the beginning, through focus, one can create a habitable order that will develop the self and establish beauty into existence.

Plus, like Peterson, the seminary rule of life emphasizes the concept of "many good games."⁸⁸ Emphasizing, the power of choice in times of incapability. For example, the discipline of study habit is a generic term with multiple ways of doing it. If a seminarian is not quite good at understanding philosophical texts, he is still able to learn through the help of his community, one that wants the best for him. He can have a "buddy system" in which one of his brother seminarians can be his partner in discussing a topic based on his learnings or takeaways. One also can listen/watch podcasts or YouTube (if he wants a verbal explanation of the text from the professionals) since the seminary gives the seminarians the privilege to use computers for study.

⁸⁶ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors' Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 13.

⁸⁷ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 128.

⁸⁸ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 110.

With that, it mends free will and determinism. There's free will in the sense of paying attention and choosing effective ways among many good games. Then there's determinism since the thing that helps a seminarian achieve its purpose is the "study discipline/the common good" given by the seminary rule of life. In fact, it enables the seminarian to create a habitable order.

e. Rule number 5: Do Not Let Your Children Do Anything That Makes You Dislike Them

Aside from a design (Seminary Rule of Life) that determines behavior, BF Skinner also emphasizes the role of planners and managers as one of the considered determiners. The planner in the seminary context can be the rector, and managers are his co-formators. For Jordan Peterson, the rector and other formators can be the parents, and the seminarians can be the children.

Furthermore, rule number 5 highlights that parents must discipline (through punishment) their children so that they will grow into well-adjusted, socially competent adults.⁸⁹ If not, Peterson argues that children grow like Aurora in *Sleeping Beauty*. Her parents tried to remove all dangerous things from her, and fairies reduced the punishment that had been cursed by Maleficent (a witch) to her. As a result, Aurora grows weak and immature.⁹⁰ Hence, a rector must discipline his seminarians. They must reinforce certain discipline with punishment. Applying the Section 4 disciplinary procedures of the seminary rule of life so that the seminarians would not grow weak as they become priests in the future.

It might sound like a strong determinism since seminarians' growth is caused by the influence of the rector. However, the discipline by the rector is not dictatorship or totalitarian. The

⁸⁹ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 160.

⁹⁰ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 150.

punishment inflicted was termed by Peterson as “Minimum Necessary Force.” Children are punished because of necessity.⁹¹ For instance, a child is about to touch a live wire, and so parents from afar will try to shout against him so that the child won’t experience a much worse case. The same also applies to the seminarians; the rector punishes them so that they won’t turn themselves worse. For example, in Section 5 (Policy on Courtship), seminarians are punished if they engage in a relationship with the opposite or same sex. Because that act is a marriage preparation, or if not, it provides fall hope to his partner (a worse experience that is unlikely to happen).⁹²

Therefore, the discipline of a rector is just a guide. It might determine seminarians’ behavior, yet it does not hinder them from their purpose. If compared to a child without a guide, they might lose track of their purpose and much worse since they lose their free will because they just allow themselves to become a slave of disorder, leading them to immaturity and weakness.

f. Rule number 6: Set Your House in Perfect Order Before You Criticize the World

Seminarians are humans too. Hence, they are also vulnerable to pain and suffering. Within the seminary, they might experience brutal conditions too. Because some are in a transitional age from teenager to adulthood. They are still young and still attached to a pleasurable thing they did in high school. Plus, their journey to adulthood triggers the need for intimacy and generativity. Sometimes, they cross the boundaries and engage with liquor or relationships. And as they are caught doing that, they are then subject to disciplinary procedures.

In that case, a seminarian might blame the seminary, or the formators, (or much worse) God, on why he experiences such things. There might be resentment within for not allowing him to

⁹¹ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 153.

⁹² Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors’ Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 29.

experience his psychological needs, and one might say, “There might be no longing if rules just allow.” However, Jordan Peterson challenges you to set your house in perfect order before you criticize the world. This is a metaphor that means that one must take responsibility for such incidents rather than blaming others. Doing that increases the sense of free will. Under the category of free will, there belongs autonomy. Autonomy is taking responsibility for the consequences of his decision. The other way around (which is blaming others) is turning a blind eye.⁹³ Like New Orleans, which was sinking under the waves of a hurricane. Yes, the hurricane is a natural order, and we can blame the cosmos or God for that matter. However, though the hurricane is natural, the failure to prepare is somehow blamed for New Orleans. Compared to the Dutch, they didn’t blame the storm for coming to their country; instead, they took responsibility; they prepared dikes so that the storm wouldn’t create flash floods that would destroy their country.⁹⁴

One of the inevitable for humans is suffering. Then, acknowledging it is a manifestation that one must be autonomous in facing the reality of life; being creative to handle things without blaming others. Furthermore, Peterson also highlights the importance of determinism in doing autonomy. He set the example of the Hebrews. At first, they inhabit a structure from God to follow, and then, as this structure leads them to fortune, corruption arises. With that, they were punished by God. Fortunately, they didn’t blame God for the punishment, but they repented. They take the blame on their own and build a structure again that might not have led them to what they were before.⁹⁵

⁹³ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 171.

⁹⁴ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 172.

⁹⁵ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 172.

The same also in the seminary; as the seminarians entered there, they were given a conference about the seminary rules. These are rules to guide the seminarians for their initial purpose, which is to become priests. But since there is an inevitable psychological need, they were tested to choose between purpose or dangerous defiance. In case of choosing defiance like drinking alcohol or being with the opposite sex for a relationship, rest assured that there is a consequence for that. If he willfully submits, he is wrong; possibly he might be forgiven or given a chance through recompense. Then, back to the structure of the rule of life so that the consequence won't happen again.

g. Rule number 7: Pursue What is Meaningful, Not What is Expedient

One of the missions of SJXXIII Seminary is “to provide young seminarians a suitable and open atmosphere for the discernment of their vocation.”⁹⁶ Discernment is choosing between two goods. That doesn't mean that becoming a seminarian is automatically toward priesthood. There must be a discernment to take; either proceed to the first purpose or try responding to the other calling of life. Both are good, but in choosing, one must consider what is better. However, aside from discernment, there is the so-called battle of choice between expedient and purpose. Expedient is an end that is practical and convenient yet improper or immoral. Whereas purpose is an end where meaning resides.

For Peterson, he preferred the so-called “delayed gratification,” in which to suffer now, celebrate later.⁹⁷ This somehow portrays a deterministic approach that allows the self to suffer in the present because of the reward reinforced in the future. For example, a seminarian sacrifices his psychological need for intimacy so that in the future he might indeed become a good priest. But

⁹⁶ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors' Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 8.

⁹⁷ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 179.

this delayed gratification also embodies the power of free choice since there is a purpose within why we prefer to suffer now. Thus, delayed gratification is a choice of purpose rather than expedient.

Actually, reinforcement occurs for both expediency and purpose. The reinforcement of purpose lies in the future, while expedient lies in the present. Examples of expedient are lying, cheating, stealing, deceiving, manipulating, and other bad things as long as one has not been caught.⁹⁸ These actions reward someone with pleasure, but that pleasure is temporary, for there are consequences. That is why, if the seminarian faces this situation in life, he can always discern. Waging what is better.

Peterson emphasizes causality through the story of Adam. After the fall, God gave him a vision to foresee the future, and this future entails he's going to die. Thus, God gives him choices: to labor, to live more (to suffer in the present so that later he would gain better reward), or to prefer pleasure and accept bad consequences later.⁹⁹ Causality entails that every decision has a consequence. It is already given, and man knows it. So, the seminarian needs to use the power of choice in discerning what reinforcement he prefers. Is it expedient or meaningful?

h. Rule number 8: Tell the Truth or at Least Don't Lie

Rule number 7 gives importance to discernment; then aligned with that is rule number 8, which highlights the importance of purifying vocation. "Tell the truth, or at least don't lie," is meant by Peterson in a literal sense. Yes, lying can be advantageous because one can manipulate others, and

⁹⁸ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 177.

⁹⁹ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 188.

manipulation can gain dominance.¹⁰⁰ You can control others, but the control caused by lying is not free will, for it eliminates all the meaning in life.

For example, a seminarian lied to the formators that he has a girlfriend. A seminarian might fool the formators, but because of his non-purified intention for his vocation, he might find life meaningless. He can't discern well, and his participation in the seminary schedule might be affected because Peterson said, "Lying weakens your character."¹⁰¹ A seminarian must be honest about its aim. Doing that sets a desirable future and a clear vision toward purpose/meaning. Lying can be a choice too but can't be considered free will because dishonesty is willful blindness; a slave of passion.¹⁰² Plus, "working at cross-purposes to your wishes, you will find yourself unmotivated and failing. You will struggle to concentrate and discipline yourself, but it will not work".¹⁰³ So, the seminarian must be honest. Either he tells his girlfriend the truth about his real purpose, which is to become a priest (in which their relationship won't work anymore) or tells the formators that he has a girlfriend (for whatever reason) and says the intention (one might leave the seminary or ask for help in decision-making.)

Moreover, in purifying such intention and in discernment, Peterson suggested that seminarians must rely on tradition because it can help seminarians establish such aims. Peterson suggests it because one might have a plan, but it might be ill-formed.¹⁰⁴ In that case, a seminarian must go first to his guidance counselor or spiritual director, where he says with all honesty about his discernment and secrets. There, he will be guided in his intentions. Plus, the submission of oneself

¹⁰⁰ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 220.

¹⁰¹ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 223.

¹⁰² Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 216.

¹⁰³ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 223.

¹⁰⁴ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 231.

to the rule of life helps the intention (to become a priest) get purified. If the seminarian is honest in giving himself to the formation, then he develops a character that prevails over a lot of adversity.

With that, a seminarian balances the life of being determined and using the power of free will. Free will, in the sense of being honest to the formation, and determinism as a guide to purify intention.

i. Rule number 9: Assume that the person you are listening to might know something you don't.

Constitutionally speaking, man has the freedom of speech. One can say what he/she wants, even his/her criticism on the sign of times. To put it in the seminary context, seminarians also have the freedom of speech. A seminarian has always had the opportunity to speak what's within his thoughts and heart. On the contrary, under such a design, a seminarian's speech is bound with limitations. He needs to be prudent in what he says, requiring him to preserve the dignity of being a seminarian. Thus, if there are instances where a seminarian goes beyond prudence, then formators will correct him during the individual colloquium. There, the seminarians will sit and listen to the evaluation that the formator has.

This is in line with Peterson's rule number 9. Listening not only demands respect (though it is), but specifically entails that one must be coachable. Yes, a seminarian can put things right around him, but not all things are known by him. He is not perfect. Thus, he must be coachable. Listen to what the formators said to him. Listen to the guidance of the counselor or spiritual director. Listen to the teacher who knows much about the lesson.

This might display no free will because the freedom of speech is hindered. But remember, freedom and free will are different. Freedom is not being under constraint, and free will is the

ability to choose an attitude in different sets of circumstances. Yes, being coachable is a deterministic act. Seminarians' behavior is caused by the formator, but it is more deterministic if they do not listen. Peterson indicates that more talking is not thinking.¹⁰⁵ In fact, it is through thinking that one can effectively use the power of free will. Through thinking, one can reflect and recall its purpose in life. Then, because of that, one can judge rightly the situation he's dealing with. Whereas talking is just allowing oneself to be a slave of ignorance. Talking triggers pride and dominance; thinking he's perfect, yet the truth is, there is more that he doesn't know. A deterministic influence that hinders the real essence of free will.

And so, a seminarian must allow himself to be determined by something that is expert to its desired purpose. Because allowing it helps him to execute his free will much better.

j. Rule number 10: Be Precise in Your Speech

Peterson highlights the importance of precision. For example, a woman would wake in pain. She might feel like dying yet not so sure, and so she has choices: either go to the hospital and tell the doctor or just stay hopeful and remain hopeful that the pain she feels will just be gone. But the problem of not telling how you feel might not articulate what you feel.¹⁰⁶ It might be cancer but neglected. Whereas telling it causes you the precision of what the pain is. You might feel frustrated knowing the truth, but at least you're prepared. "Precision may leave the tragedy intact, but it chases away the ghouls and the demons."¹⁰⁷

To put it in the seminary context, seminarians are also encouraged to be precise, not just in speech but also in their purpose in life. Among the possibilities he may have in the future, what

¹⁰⁵ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 256.

¹⁰⁶ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 284.

¹⁰⁷ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 284.

was the reason why he aspired to be a priest? One might say, I want to become a priest because I want to save souls. Well, that's one, but priesthood is more than that. Sometimes, it requires martyrdom; you have to be early for morning prayer; you have to study a lot so that you can share more knowledge with people during your homily; you need to persevere since formation will take long years; you need to be zealous so that you can say mass even to the remote areas, etc. Now that priesthood is articulated, one might change paths; maybe I won't be a priest anymore; I want now a married life. Then, that's good discernment, but you have to articulate marriage again. One might realize marriage is not just intimacy; sometimes it is quarrels, cold moments, tiredness, and more.

What's the point is that every path in life has flaws. But remember rule number 6 (don't blame it; blame yourself). Now, one might feel unworthy to achieve such a purpose. Like, for example, I can't be a priest because I am not zealous, but where are you going then? Maybe go to married life; now you also discover the flaws of entering that life. So, what is your purpose?

Now Peterson encourages that one must determine where you have been in your life.¹⁰⁸ Since a seminarian precisely articulates every choice in life, now he must make a stand. Again, precision will leave a tragedy, but this opens one's eyes to reality and so practice well the power of free will. Yes, allowing the self to experience beyond expected might be a determinism. From a simple intention of saving souls, now he needs to do other things as a requirement in line with that simple intention. However, free will still exists by making a stand for that.

Peterson encourages: Say what you mean so that you can find out what you mean. (Now this is articulating your purpose.) Act out what you say, so you can find out what happens. Then pay

¹⁰⁸ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 286.

attention. Note your errors. Articulate them. Strive to correct them. That is how you discover the meaning of your life.¹⁰⁹

A seminarian must specify his destination (that's free will), and towards his journey, he needs a chart that courses him toward its purpose (that's determinism).

k. Rule number 11: Do not bother Children When they are Skateboarding

In this rule, it emphasizes the power of free will within the supervision of authority. Peterson shared a story about a child who is skateboarding. He does stunts that are dangerous but allow him to enhance bravery.¹¹⁰ Plus, Peterson highlights that compassion is a vice.¹¹¹ Spoiling the child out of danger might cause immaturity and weaken his/her character. The child might not create autonomy and always rely upon its parent. As a result, as that child grows up, he will lack autonomy, always agreeing to the suggestions given by others despite those things being wrong. Peterson called it the losing way.

That's the problem with strong determinism. It weakens the character. Fortunately, in the seminary, seminarians are ensured that the rule of life did not spoil them. Despite its presence, seminarians are still encouraged to be brave enough in decision-making. They are allowed to explore and face challenges so that they may enhance their creativity and confidence. Section 7 of the Seminary Rule of Life indicates the seminary offices where seminarians are given an office to manage.¹¹² Despite that, the offices have roles to follow, but the purpose of it is to allow the seminarian to become autonomous. Allowing them to be creative in how to manage their office

¹⁰⁹ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 286.

¹¹⁰ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 289.

¹¹¹ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 318.

¹¹² Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors' Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 44.

and how to implement certain activities. They are allowed to experience the danger of criticism and the challenge to face it with might. For example, the office of the socio-sports coordinator. They are the ones who will initiate sports and social activities. To create is somehow fearful, for it may not be enjoyable for others. But one proposed it with might, and maybe there would be criticism about the activity, but one's character is sharpened. He executes his free will, and if criticism occurs, then there's the benefit of rule number 9, in which one should listen. Avoiding being a slave of ignorance. The seminarian mightily explores the consequences of his decision. Though fearsome yet worthwhile.

Additionally, this can be applicable also in discernment. For example, the discernment between marriage life and priesthood. Seminarians who decide to be in a relationship with a woman are not spoiled by the formator. The seminarian is not dragged out of the situation because that is dangerous for the goal of the priesthood; instead, number 7 of Section 5 is provided (where the seminarian has options.)¹¹³ Among the options he chooses, the consequence must be fearful, but he needs to face it with might. And with that, the seminarian executes his free will since he accomplished his purpose without being spoiled by the formators. Then, in line with Rule 8, the seminarian becomes honest with himself, and that's a good thing. However, note that Peterson suggests the importance of tradition in guiding our might, because sometimes this "might" be ill-formed. So, seminarians and the deterministic rule of life must coexist for a meaningful life.

L. Rule number 12: Pet a Cat When You Encounter One on the Street

Peterson defines the difference between a dog and a cat. Dogs are tamable, and you can gain their loyalty, while cats are semi-domesticated.¹¹⁴ One might tame a cat or not. Just bear in mind

¹¹³ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors' Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 30.

¹¹⁴ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 348.

that they create their own decisions, and this reflects society. People and events around us are cats. We cannot predict people's emotions and can't predict the future. Yes, we can do something; either we kick that cat or bend down and show a little kindness towards it. But still, something is unpredictable. And this indicates things are out of control.

The last rule simply entails that in life, things go upside down. Despite all the efforts to tame a cat, we don't know what will happen next. Previous rules are a good help to live life meaningfully. They highlight that what we do in the present has a consequence, and it is in our hands where everything relies. Some cases might be like that, but what if some cases turn upside down? What if the seminarian did his best to follow the rule of life so that he could accomplish his purpose in life, but things automatically change? He is given a special program. His ordination got extended, then how would he cope with that considering that he submitted himself well to the rules given previously and still failed?

Well, Peterson suggests that one must still try despite unpredictability. Pay attention even to bad moments; maybe one can be fortunate enough to explore opportunities.¹¹⁵ Appreciate the moment and act positively towards it. One might consider bending down and acting kindly to that cat. Maybe that cat will be tamed or not; at least you try.

Yes, out-of-control moments and surroundings might be a deterministic act. A seminarian has nothing to do with it but note that free will is not freedom where you can do anything without being under constraint. Free will is choosing an attitude to respond in such a situation. And so, even if the seminarian is required to extend, he can freely choose to find joy within the situation or be discouraged. He is still free to try. And that's the important thing. Even though we followed

¹¹⁵ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 349.

the 11 rules previously, sometimes life turns us upside down and we need a backup rule, which is the last rule: pet a cat or pet in an unpredictable situation.

3. The co-existence of BF Skinner, Viktor Frankl, and Jordan Peterson in the Seminary Formation

BF Skinner's operant conditioning and Viktor Frankl's logotherapy are two opposing arguments. However, Jordan Peterson mends the rift through the balance of chaos and order. This entails that although the primary source of the behavior is man's purpose in life, as a human, there are instances where this will of ours is still immature. Without nurturing this will, one's purpose will be blurry. Considering what Jordan Peterson said that under chaos is man's will since our adventure in life is not fixed as it is.¹¹⁶ There are still possibilities that could change our desires in life. So, one must nurture it. One needs rules as a guiding star toward adventure. One needs fertilizer to make the seed mature and fruitful. Order must be with chaos.

Viktor Frankl might have a good claim for us to live life meaningfully because, through purpose, we are free. However, we can't deny that BF Skinner is necessary. One must have an external factor that leads inner will toward its purpose. Like, for example, in the Gospel (Mark 10:17–31). The rich young man desired to follow Christ but could not accept the requirement of Christ whom he followed. One alone might be effective in some cases, but it is much more effective if both determinism and free will coexist. Imagine, on the one hand, free will alone exists, and then man is no destination to arrive at. On the other hand, if determinism alone exists, man is like a robot.

¹¹⁶ Peterson, *12 Rules for Life*, 22.

In the seminary context, a seminarian cannot say he will become a priest if he does not submit himself to the formation of the seminary Rule of Life. His desire needs discipline so that, if he becomes a priest, he is essentially a priest. Thus, he needs to submit himself to whatever the Seminary Rule of Life is saying. Plus, the Seminary Rule of Life manifests its guidance through the schedule so that seminarians already inhabit the life that a priest is experiencing. Within a week, seminarians habitually have three sets of schedules: the weekdays, Saturday, and Sunday.

a. Weekdays start with a “rising” at 5:00 am, where seminarians will wake up and prepare themselves (through bathing and stretching). 5:15 am will be an integrated mass and lauds (morning prayer). After that, breakfast will follow at 6:00 am. Then 6:30 will be the departure from the seminary to San Isidro College for class schedules. Each batch has different class schedules, but as a community, together we will go home at 5:30 pm. As they arrive home, evening prayer follows at 6:30 pm. 7:00 pm-7:30 pm will be the dinner. Afterward, lighthouse cleaning follows from 7:30 pm to 7:45 pm. 7:45 until 8:30 will be the recreation, where seminarians play indoor sports or play music. 8:30 until 9:00 pm will be the night prayer. Then 9:00 pm until 10:30 will be personal time. Either do study or do something else like washing clothes, room cleaning, etc. 10:30 will be lights off and grand silence.

For seminarians, rising is a bit early and tedious since next is the integrated mass and morning prayer, but this is because to become a priest, a seminarian must prepare himself already before others do. While the people of God are still asleep, a priest is already waking up, preparing himself to pray for those who sleep. And since a seminarian aspires to be a priest, he must habit a life like that.

In the class schedules, seminarians are required to study, specifically, the philosophy course, so that seminarians will enhance their analytical and critical minds.¹¹⁷ It is necessary to enhance it because it is evident in a priest's life the need to be analytical, in particular in the sign of times. The priest is a pastor too, and as a pastor, he oversees taking good care of the parish (people). With the knowledge he has, he can address issues of people or society such as divorce, same-sex marriage, contraceptives, etc. Without studying, being a pastor is difficult.

In the evening, prayer is always important. This helps the seminarian develop a sense of the sacred in life.¹¹⁸ It is because priesthood is a call to be a spiritual leader, and how can he lead the people if he has no spirituality?

Recreation is also necessary. This helps the seminarian to develop one's talent, promote camaraderie and brotherhood, enhance self-confidence, and promote healthy relaxation.¹¹⁹ It is necessary to live that kind of life because the nature of a leader (a spiritual leader) is not always authoritarian but sometimes fun. Peterson gives the example of the chimpanzee's leadership. The alpha chimpanzee might be the smallest in the troop, but his leadership is not based on power and force but on social relations and making peace.¹²⁰ And so is the priest too. In fact, priest leadership is by way of recreation or having fun with others.

b. During Saturday's seminarians don't have class; hence, activities are more on the seminary premises. Similarly, they wake up early. This time they wake up at 4:45 am because 5:00 am will be the BEC session. At 6:00 am, the seminarians will have their mass at Carmelites Monastery (a

¹¹⁷ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors' Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 13.

¹¹⁸ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors' Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 11.

¹¹⁹ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors' Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 10.

¹²⁰ Jordan B. Peterson, "Chimpanzees and The Theory of Power, Social Structure and Reproduction| With Karl Friston," Jordan B. Peterson Clips, posted on October 28, 2022, YouTube Video, 0: 37, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mhz8ekbDhQ8>

neighboring religious congregation). After the mass, at 8:00 am will be breakfast. Then, from 9:00 am to 10:30 am, there will be the *laburandom* (general cleaning) at the particular areas of the seminary. Either sickle the tall grasses, clean the hall, plant trees, or do something else. 11:45 am is the meditation, and 12:00 pm is lunch. 1:00 pm to 2:30 pm will be the siesta. 3:00 pm to 4:30 pm is the sports. 5:30 pm to 7:00 pm is the music practice. 7:00 pm is dinner. 8:00 pm is the film viewing. After the movie will be the lights off and grand silence.

Similarly to recreation, sports and film viewing promote relaxation and camaraderie. Forming the seminarian to be a friendly priest in the future. Without developing that virtue, how can people ask for the aid of a priest if people feel that they are not welcome?

BEC session: “Develop the love of the scriptures, openness in sharing their personal experiences in the light of the Gospel, their sense of communion as a small community, and love for the Church.”¹²¹ This formation helps the seminarian reflect on the scriptures not just through objective/intellectual learning but also the personal/subjective experience. Integrating the two (objective and subjective) because, in the priesthood, a priest does not lecture people but does a homily (a sermon) that empathizes with people’s issues and situations.

Laburandum is telling that seminarians must also inhabit the attitude of cleanliness. As a spiritual leader, it is necessary to be a model for others, especially in being a “steward of God’s creation” (Genesis 2:15). Plus, this develops the attitude of the industry since a priest “promotes the dignity of human labor”¹²² By also practicing work. Thus, a seminarian must also work, even in a simple way of cleaning.

¹²¹ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors’ Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 13.

¹²² Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors’ Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 10.

c. Sunday is the day of the mission where seminarians have their pastoral program. Each batch has its different pastoral programs. The first-year and second-year seminarians have their Chapel BEC Apostolate, where they do BEC sessions with the people in the assigned chapel. Third-year seminarians have their hospital exposure where they distribute the sacred host (the Body of Christ) to the sick since they can't go to church for the moment. And the fourth-year seminarians have the DXDB media Apostolate. It is a radio program where seminarians share their song reflection as a way of evangelization whose target is the youth."¹²³

Like a priest, Sunday is the day of service. Unlike lay people who have their day off on Sunday, priests don't have a day off. Instead, they must go the extra mile because their main goal is to care for the soul of people, not the self. In the Council of Trent, Pope Paul III published that the office of a priest is *Cura Animarum* (care for the soul).¹²⁴ Hence, a seminarian must inhabit the virtue of pastoral because achieving the purpose of priesthood entails self-sacrifice for others.

¹²³ Seminary Commission and Seminary Consultors' Board, *Seminary Rule of Life*, 15.

¹²⁴ Council Fathers, "Decree on Reformation," *General Council of Trent 23*, no. 1 (1563): 178, <https://www.papalencyclicals.net/councils/trent/twenty-third-session.htm>.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

The study analyzes if there is a reconciliation between free will and determination. The researcher utilized BF Skinner's operant conditioning, Viktor Frankl's logotherapy, and Jordan Peterson's pragmatic psychology (particularly his book 12 Rules for Life). Then the researcher distinguished Determinism from free will, in particular in the seminary context. The determinism of BF Skinner is related to the Seminary Rule of Life and the Seminary Formators. While Viktor Frankl's Free Will is related to the seminarians. Moreover, aside from differences, the researchers also distinguished the relationship between the two using Jordan Peterson.

The researcher discovered that Determinism and free will can be mended together. Jordan Peterson acknowledges both BF Skinner and Viktor Frankl in his book 12 Rules for Life. Emphasizing the importance of balancing order (determinism) and chaos (free will) in life. Entailing that as a seminarian adventure to the unexpected world (chaos), he needs structure (order) that guides him throughout his journey. Furthermore, the researcher discussed each rule to analyze well the interplay of determinism and free will in a detailed manner. As the researcher delves into each rule, the researcher finds out that the seminary rule of life that determined the seminarians is actually aiding them to be free and helping them away from the slavery of ignorance and passion.

Lastly, the researcher sought the relevance of mending the three claims from BF Skinner, Viktor Frankl, and Jordan Peterson. The researcher finds out that one alone makes the seminarian

a slave. Either a slave of external factors due to determinism or a slave of immature will. So, both are necessary.

Conclusion

The problem of opposites can be found as hard to mend. Just like the problem of free will and determinism. They are diametrically opposite. The idea goes like this: if one is determined, one has no free will because one's behavior is not caused by his own. And if one has free will, then one is not determined because one's behavior is caused by the inner self. Nevertheless, note that this research highlighted the relevance of mending the two variables. Through the ideas of BF Skinner, Viktor Frankl, and Jordan Peterson, it is indeed true that there is an interplay between free will and determinism, despite being opposite. In particular, to put it in the seminary context.

BF Skinner posits that behavior is caused by rules. For Viktor Frankl, behavior is caused by an inner drive for meaning. And Jordan Peterson highlights the importance of balancing chaos and harmony. With these three, it is clear that seminary formations are a harmony of determinism and free will. The primary drive of the seminarian's behavior is their purpose to become priests (Viktor Frankl), but it cannot be denied the necessity of rules to guide the non-purified will (BF Skinner). Thus, a balance between chaos and harmony (Jordan Peterson.)

Recommendation

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, understanding the interplay of determinism and free will is essential as the foundation of living. With that, the researcher proposes the following recommendations:

The society (the government as well as the citizens) must agree on good rules and regulations that would discipline towards a meaningful life. Thus, before proposing a bill, one must reflect if the bill causes a meaningful life to all the citizens, or maybe it is just out of personal bias. If, by chance, a bill is proposed, government officials must consider the mend existential philosophy of BF Skinner, Viktor Frankl, and Jordan Peterson, that rules are only to guide, not to manipulate. Plus, the citizens must abide by the law so that those ill-formed wills would be shaped into a real mature free will. And they would be directed toward a meaningful life.

The seminary must let their seminarians understand that they should not be confused about whether they have free will inside the seminary or not, for the seminary rule of life is just a guide for them, not to make them feel that they are like prisoners. This guide enables them to live a meaningful life within and/or outside the seminary.

The future interested researcher must also reconcile the other kinds of determinism, in particular, theological determinism. The topic entails God knows everything, even the future, and since He knows the future, it always happens. As fate is already in the script of life, then free will can be questionable. Researching that topic is essential to the field of philosophy since seeking reconciliation between theological determinism and man's free will can give a reference that maybe can heal someone's doubt.

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